

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) op-8-47

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: op-8-47

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0055 A Wavelength=1.54184

Cell: a=12.5787(4) b=13.2453(5) c=27.0193(7)
 alpha=84.868(2) beta=77.958(2) gamma=63.112(3)
Temperature: 140 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	3926.6(2)	3926.6(2)
Space group	P -1	P -1
Hall group	-P 1	-P 1
Moiety formula	C54 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, C16 H32 K O7, 4(C4 H8 O)	C54 H34 B2 Co N6 O6, C16 H32 K O7, 4(C4 H8 O)
Sum formula	C86 H98 B2 Co K N6 O17	C86 H98 B2 Co K N6 O17
Mr	1607.35	1607.35
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.360	1.359
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	2.796	2.796
F000	1696.0	1696.0
F000'	1697.02	
h,k,lmax	16,16,34	15,16,33
Nref	17240	16040
Tmin,Tmax	0.433,0.788	0.113,0.662
Tmin'	0.067	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.113 Tmax=0.662
AbsCorr = ANALYTICAL

Data completeness= 0.930 Theta(max)= 80.805

R(reflections)= 0.0681(13789) wR2(reflections)= 0.1925(16040)

S = 1.068 Npar= 1074

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT243_ALERT_4_C	High	'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C84	Check
PLAT243_ALERT_4_C	High	'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C91	Check
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short	Intra H...H Contact H12 ..H15 .	1.96	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short	Intra H...H Contact H26 ..H29 .	1.96	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check
PLAT410_ALERT_2_C	Short	Intra H...H Contact H40 ..H43 .	1.95	Ang.
		x,y,z =	1_555	Check
PLAT906_ALERT_3_C	Large	K Value in the Analysis of Variance	2.284	Check
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing	FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L= 0.600	117	Report

● **Alert level G**

PLAT003_ALERT_2_G	Number of Uiso or Uij Restrained non-H Atoms ...	10	Report
PLAT063_ALERT_4_G	Crystal Size Possibly too Large for Beam Size ..	0.92	mm
PLAT178_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains SIMU Records	1	Report
PLAT187_ALERT_4_G	The CIF-Embedded .res File Contains RIGU Records	1	Report
PLAT302_ALERT_4_G	Anion/Solvent/Minor-Residue Disorder (Resd 2)	21%	Note
PLAT302_ALERT_4_G	Anion/Solvent/Minor-Residue Disorder (Resd 3)	20%	Note
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C7 -C20 .	1.45	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C21 -C34 .	1.45	Ang.
PLAT333_ALERT_2_G	Large Aver C6-Ring C-C Dist C35 -C48 .	1.45	Ang.
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O17	108.8	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O15	109.4	Degree
PLAT398_ALERT_2_G	Deviating C-O-C Angle From 120 for O18	104.7	Degree
PLAT860_ALERT_3_G	Number of Least-Squares Restraints	210	Note
PLAT910_ALERT_3_G	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s) Below Theta(Min).	1	Note
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L= 0.600	1033	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ...	4	Note
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G	Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity	2.7	Low
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.	5	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
7 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
18 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
12 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
5 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
8 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
0 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 18/09/2020; check.def file version of 20/08/2020

